

DETERMINATION OF INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITE MATERIALS IN STATIC AND FATIGUE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

This research explores modified testing techniques for measuring interlaminar shear strength S_{yz} for orthotropic composite materials. Measurement of this out-of-plane property is essential for complete three-dimensional analyses of laminated composite materials. Existing shear test methods are designed primarily for measuring static strength in the x-y plane (S_{xy}), which is essentially similar to the interlaminar shear strength in the x-z plane for most orthotropic materials. New test methods are developed here to measure interlaminar shear strength S_{yz} under both static and fatigue loading conditions. Interlaminar shear strength can be measured by careful choice of specimen configuration and testing method. The tests are not easy to conduct because of the relatively small magnitude of S_{yz} compared to S_{xz} . The testing techniques are verified by finite element stress analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of full three-dimensional analysis for the stress and failure analysis of composite materials has been made possible by the availability of high-speed computing capability. However, composite material models in three dimensions require more material parameters than those needed for two-dimensional laminated composite plate theory. In this research, a test method is devised to measure interlaminar shear strength (S_{yz}) as a necessary contribution to a complete set of material properties. Figure 1 depicts a specially orthotropic material, and shows that there are essentially two planes which have similar material appearance: the x-y plane and the x-z plane. The similarity of these two material planes reduces the number of independent properties (stiffness, strength and Poisson's ratio) from eighteen to eleven. Of the shear properties, strength S_{xy} and S_{xz} are similar. The shear strength S_{yz} is different and tends to be weaker than the other two shear strengths. Accordingly, the test methods suitable for measuring S_{xy} and S_{xz} are not applicable to S_{yz} , thus another test method must be developed.

Fig. 1 Three dimensional geometry of a layer of composite material

Interlaminar shear strength is defined as the shear strength at rupture in which the plane of fracture is located between the layers of reinforcement of a plastic reinforced structure [1]. This is of particular significance for predicting the strength of a material, so a reliable, simple method must be found for which both the static and the fatigue interlaminar shear strengths can be tested. The method must be able to determine the life as well as the residual strength of the material without being too expensive to fabricate or to test. In addition, using complicated fixtures must be avoided because of probable induced damage to them in fatigue loading. The four main methods for determining the interlaminar shear strength of a material are the short beam shear test [2-6], the four-point shear test [6,7], the Iosipescu test [6,9-12] and the notched coupon [1,6,8,13-15].

Different authors have shown the short beam shear test [2-6], and four point shear test [6-7] are not reliable test methods, moreover a pure interlaminar shear stress can not be induced which results a complex fracture [8]. Also to measure the interlaminar shear strength (S_{yz}), by utilizing these methods, a 90° unidirectional ply must be used. It is clear that a 90° unidirectional ply can fail in matrix failure mode, caused by σ_{yy} , before failure happens under interlaminar shear stress σ_{yz} . Therefore it is very difficult to use these methods to measure the interlaminar shear strength (S_{yz}).

The Iosipescu testing method has been examined extensively [6,9-11]. Many investigators verified the Iosipescu testing method as a highly effective and reliable method. However measuring the interlaminar shear strength (S_{yz}) of a unidirectional ply by this method is difficult. First, a complicated fixture is needed to perform the test, which makes the method cumbersome. Moreover the fixture can be damaged during fatigue tests. It is clear that to measure the interlaminar shear strength (S_{yz}) of a unidirectional ply, by the Iosipescu testing method, a 90° ply must be used. However an investigation by Ho *et. al* [10] shows a mixed mode failure for a 90° specimen due to out-of-plane rotation of the specimen. Investigations by Chang *et. al* [11], and Ho *et. al* [10] show the failure does not initiate along the notch section of the specimen.

Unlike the Iosipescu test, the notched coupon requires no extensive set-up or fixture and is a simple test. These features make the double notched test method attractive for fatigue testing. Markham and Dawson [8] performed a study of the notched coupon test and they concluded that the specimen always fails in shear. They also report the finding of consistent results with fracture occurring in a single plane unlike the complex fracture occurring with the short beam test. These results and the simplicity of the testing method in static and fatigue loading conditions lead to the belief that this may be an appropriate testing method. There are some disadvantages mentioned in the literature about this testing method which are summarized in the following. Munjal [6] found that it was difficult to control the notch depth in the notched coupon test and thus had quite a scatter of results. Chiao *et al.* [12] postulate that the shear strength data obtained in by this testing method was lower than that by other methods. Tarnopol'skii and Kincis [13] discuss the disadvantages of this test method by testing samples with nonsymmetrically placed notches, the fixtures for prevention of specimen bending are necessary and high sensitivity to the accuracy of cutting the notches. This study examines all the disadvantages postulated by other authors, and shows that all these difficulties can be eliminated by selecting a proper geometry found by finite element analysis.

DESCRIPTION OF THE PROBLEM

Given the absence of a standard testing method for interlaminar shear strength, it is desired to find the premium technique for this purpose. For this reason, the notched specimen test is selected as suggested in the ASTM Standard D 3846-79 reapproved 1985 [14] for reinforced plastics and further investigated in the ASTM Standard D 2733-70 [1] for reinforced plastics at elevated temperatures. This standard suggests two methods for finding shear strengths. Method A requires that a clamp be placed at the midsection of the specimen for a distance of 65 mm and tightened evenly so as not to damage the specimen. This should result in an interlaminar shear-type failure. Method B does not require a clamp and is tested in tension to failure. This method is less desirable since it is known that the material is weaker in matrix tension than in interlaminar shear loading. If a tensile load is used with a 90° lay-up, then catastrophic matrix failure would occur prior to failure in interlaminar shear. Method A will be referred to as clamped and method B will be referred to as unclamped. It is desired to study the behaviour of a double notched sample under these two testing conditions. This is performed by applying a finite element analysis and through an experimental program.

The behaviour of the double lap shear specimen is similar to the notched coupon, with interlaminar shear failure being introduced at the interface of two layers. The previous results [15] showed a non uniform stress region over the failed area but were influenced by large and almost equal shear stress concentrations at each end of the failure plane which resulted in a variation in the shear stresses. It is thus desired to see whether these results also occur in a notched specimen and what effect variations of the notch size has on the results. Various testing programs are also analyzed, including using a specimen of pure 90° layers or a hybrid of 90° layers being supported by 0° layers. Analysis is also performed to see if better results are obtained from testing the sample in tension or compression, with or without clamp.

A coupon of dimensions as given in figure 2 was considered. The coupon was a laminated composite plate consisting of 16 or 24 layers. The composite plate configuration is either $[0_6/90_2]_s$ or $[90_{24}]$. These configurations were selected based on the following reasons. In order to induce

interlaminar shear (σ_{yz}) in the gage area of a double notched specimen, a 90° lay-up must be used. However, the material is weaker in matrix tension than in interlaminar shear loading. Therefore, a tensile load applied to a double notch specimen with 90° lay-up results in a matrix failure prior to failure in interlaminar shear. There are two solutions to this problem. The first solution is to use $[0/90]_s$ laminate instead of a 90° lay-up. However it is known that the strength of the material in matrix compression loading is higher than in matrix tension. Therefore the second solution is to apply a compressive load instead of a tensile load on a 90° lay-up. Improbability of failure between the 0 and 90° plies is the disadvantage of using $[0/90]_s$ laminate. The disadvantage of the second method is the possibility of buckling, which can be avoided by using clamps (as shown in Fig. 3).

	a (mm)	W (mm)	d (mm)	l (mm)	t (mm)
w_1, w_2, w_3	66.675	1.13, 2.29, 4.57	1.59	6.35	3.18
d_1, d_2, d_3	66.675	2.29	1.52, 1.59, 1.66	6.35	3.18
l_1	63.500	2.29	1.59	12.70	3.18
l_2	66.675	2.29	1.59	6.35	3.18
l_3	68.262	2.29	1.59	3.175	3.18
t_{16}, t_{24}, t_{32}	66.675	2.29	1.06, 1.59, 2.17	6.35	2.12, 3.18, 4.33

Fig. 2. Specimen dimensions showing all possible configurations

The effect of notch width was first examined since Tarnopol'skii *et al.* [13] who states that the double notch shear test is very sensitive to the accuracy of cutting the notches. To examine this difficulty, three different widths: w_1 , w_2 , and w_3 are analyzed in this study. Another disadvantage given by Munjal [6] and Chaio *et al.* [12], of the double notched shear test is said to be the difficulty in accurately cutting the notches to the prescribed depth (see figure 2). Thus a study was undertaken to analyze the depth by testing three different notch depths: d_1 , d_2 , and d_3 . These depths correspond to half of the thickness of the specimen, an overcut (too deep), or an undercut (too shallow). The distance at which the notches are cut (Fig. 2) is also variable due to the difficulty in machining the specimen accurately. Thus three distances between the notches were examined: l_1 , l_2 , and l_3 . The final analysis was to determine the effect of the specimen thickness. Three specimen thicknesses were examined: t_{16} , t_{24} , and t_{32} , corresponding to either 16, 24, or 32 plies. Due to the difficulty in manufacturing thick specimens, more than 32 plies was not feasible. Less than 16 plies, was also undesirable due to its sensitivity to external effects, including buckling.

Fig. 3 Clamp used to eliminate the out-of-plane buckling

The material used in this study is AS4/3501-6 with the following material properties: longitudinal modulus ($E_{xx} = 150$. GPa), transverse or normal modulus ($E_{yy} = E_{zz} = 8$. GPa), in-plane shear modulus ($E_{xy} = E_{zx} = 5$. GPa), out-of-plane shear modulus ($E_{yz} = 6$. GPa), Poisson's ratios ($\nu_{xy} = \nu_{zx} = \nu_{yz} = .3$), transverse or normal tensile strength ($Y_t = Z_t = 53.98$ MPa), transverse or normal compressive strength ($Y_c = Z_c = 203.69$ MPa) and the interlaminar shear strength ($S_{yz} = 42$ MPa, as measured in this study). The properties have been measured at McGill University.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

To predict the behaviour of the notched coupon, a stress analysis is performed using SDRC I-DEAS finite element software [16]. The specimen was modeled using eight-node quadrilateral

isoparametric elements. Since the stresses between the two notches are of main interest, elements were concentrated in this area.

BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

By considering the plane stress conditions in y-z plane (Fig. 2), a cross section of the specimen can be modeled by finite element techniques. Since there is no symmetry with respect to y-axis, the entire cross section of the specimen in y-z plane is modeled. The boundary conditions for the unclamped case are shown in figure 4(a). One end of the specimen is fixed and an edge pressure is applied on the thickness at the other end. Moreover to simulate the gripped ends in the testing machine, the displacement of the nodes in the gripped area were fixed in z-direction (Fig. 4(a)).

Fig. 4 Load and displacement boundary conditions

The displacement field of the nodes under the clamp area is examined for the unclamped model (Fig. 5). The out-of-plane buckling, observed by finite element analysis and by experimental techniques, is due to the antisymmetric geometry of the specimen. To eliminate this behaviour a simple clamp (Fig. 3) is used. To simulate the clamped case in the finite element model, fixed displacement boundary conditions in z-direction are applied on proper nodes in the clamped region (Fig. 4(b))

Fig. 5. Displacement field of the unclamped specimen

RESULTS OF FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The results of the finite element analysis are presented here for various notch widths, depths, lengths and specimen thickness.

Loading Analysis

ASTM Standard D 2733-70 [1] suggests tensile loading with or without a clamp, method A and B. The specimen in tension created positive σ_{yy} and σ_{zz} stresses whereas the specimen in compression created negative σ_{yy} and σ_{zz} stresses. Since the material, in matrix direction, is weaker in tension than in compression it is desired to keep the normal stresses negative, so that they do not cause failure. Thus the compression test was chosen. The results of the stress analysis of the specimen with or without a clamp under compressive loading are shown in figure 6. The stresses in the gage area, between notches, from point A to B (Fig. 2) are plotted (Fig. 6). The results indicate that the σ_{yy} and σ_{zz} stresses in the gage area were reduced by adding the clamp and the stress concentrations at the notch tips were reduced. As shown in figure 6, the stresses are normalized with respect to the related strength. To normalize σ_{yy} and σ_{zz} stresses, they were divided by the strength in transverse direction (Y) which is assumed to be equal to the strength in normal direction (Z). The tensile stresses are normalized by tensile strength and compressive stresses are normalized by compressive strength. The interlaminar shear stress (σ_{yz}) is normalized by the interlaminar shear strength. The σ_{yz} stress exhibited the same behaviour with lower stress concentrations at the notches and the adding the clamp increased the shear stress in the gage area which is favored. The clamped specimen or method A tested in compression is thus the preferred case and is considered from here on.

changes the state of stresses, however the state of stress is not sensitive to small amount of variation of the notch length. Therefore the effect of small variation of the notch length is not a critical parameter.

Fig. 9 The results of stress analysis of different notch lengths

Effect of the Specimen Thickness

The specimen thickness effect was then investigated (Fig. 10). For this study, three thicknesses were examined which corresponds to t_{16} , t_{24} , and t_{32} , or 16 plies, 24 plies and 32 plies. It was determined that by increasing the amount of layers the transverse and normal stresses (σ_{yy} and σ_{zz}) remained the same. However the interlaminar shear stress (σ_{yz}) increases with increasing the number of plies. It is concluded that to perform a better test, the number of plies should be increased.

Fig. 10 The results of stress analysis of different specimen thickness

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

MANUFACTURING OF SPECIMENS

The specimens used in this research were made of AS4/3501-6. For both $[0_6/90_2]_s$ and for $[90_{24}]$ unidirectional prepreg sheets were aligned and processed in an autoclave. The individual specimens were then cut from the sheets to the length and width as described in figure 2 using a diamond impregnated saw. A critical aspect of the manufacturing was the cutting of the notches. Since some tolerances exist in the thickness from the curing process the average width of each specimen in the gage area was found and divided in half. After clamping the specimen into the milling machine the depth was then cut into the specimen at one end using a fast speed (1500 rpm) and small depth increments to reduce microcracking. The same process was then used on the other side to a depth of the total thickness minus the depth of the existing notch.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND SPECIFICATIONS OF TEST SPECIMENS

Tests were performed using the MTS, material testing system, equipped with hydraulic grips and computerized for data acquisition. Displacement, and load were monitored for static experiments. In fatigue tests, maximum and minimum displacement, and load as well as number of cycles were monitored. Static tests were performed under displacement control, while the fatigue tests were carried out under load control conditions. To avoid temperature effects, which could degrade the material properties, fatigue tests were performed at frequencies less than 10 Hz. All tests were performed in ambient temperature. A simple clamp is used to eliminate the out-of-plane buckling caused by the antisymmetric geometry of the specimen (Fig. 3). The nuts of the clamp were tightened with a torque wrench to $.113+0.000,-0.028$ N m.

Fig. 6 Stress analysis of clamped and unclamped specimen

Effect of the Notch Width

The effect of the notch widths w_1 , w_2 and w_3 were examined (Fig. 7). The dimensions are given in figure 2. The variation of the notch width does not alter the σ_{yy} , σ_{zz} and σ_{yz} stresses significantly. This indicates that the notch width does not have an important influence on specimen strength.

Fig. 7 The results of stress analysis of different notch widths

Effect of the Notch Depth

The depth of the notches at d_1 , d_2 , and d_3 were examined. It would seem likely that if the depth of the notch is more than half the depth of the specimen, or overcut, then bending stresses occur in the gage area. Also, if the depth of the notch is less than half the depth of the specimen, or undercut, then compressive stresses occur in the gage area. To examine the exact effect of the notch depth, stress analysis for different notch depths is performed and it was determined that the difference of depth did not effect the stresses in the gage area, but alters the stresses at the notch edge (Fig. 8). Deeper notches caused lower negative σ_{yy} stress but higher negative σ_{zz} stress. Shallower notches caused higher positive σ_{yy} stress, but lower σ_{zz} stress. Both effects in the clamped case are still below failure. Shear stress exhibits the same behaviour with varying stresses at the notch edge. Thus it can be concluded that if the notch depth varies slightly, it will not effect the results and this is not a critical parameter. This is also verified experimentally.

Fig. 8 The results of stress analysis of different notch depths

Effect of the Length between Notches

The results in figure 8 indicate that if the distance between the notches is too close then higher σ_{yy} and σ_{zz} stresses exist and the interlaminar shear stress, σ_{yz} , is also higher. The further the notches are apart, the lower the normal and the shear stresses are achieved. Therefore a proper notch length can be selected by examining the transverse and normal stresses (σ_{yy} and σ_{zz}) and the strength of the material in these to directions. Although making the notch length double or half

Based on the finite element analysis of different samples, the $[90_{12}]_s$ lay-up with a notch width of $w = 2.286$ mm, notch depth of $d = 1.5875$ mm, notch distance of $l = 6.35$ mm, and total length of $L = 139.7$ mm (Fig. 2) was selected for the experimental studies.

RESULTS OF STATIC AND FATIGUE TESTS

The results of static experiments for measuring the strength of the material under out-of-plane shear loading are summarized in Table 1. By considering the reasonable standard deviation achieved, it is concluded the experimental scatter is acceptable and test method is reliable for measuring the interlaminar shear strength of the material. It must be mentioned that a series of $[0_6/90_2]_s$ specimens were tested under static and fatigue loading conditions, however the final failure for this configuration occurs at the interface between 0 and 90 degree plies. Therefore the results of these experiments can not be used as the interlaminar shear strength of a unidirectional ply. Hence the results of the experiments are not considered here.

Specimen Code	Strength (MPa)	Specimen Code	Strength (MPa)	Specimen Code	Strength (MPa)
6S-1	39.54	S-6	S-11	S-16	40.90
S-2	36.36	S-7	S-12	S-17	43.23
S-3	34.48	S-8	S-13	S-18	37.80
S-4	39.94	S-9	S-14	S-19	49.91
S-5	40.06	S-10	S-15		

Mean = 41.88
Standard deviation= 5.065

Table 1. Static strength for out-of-plane shear

The fatigue experiments were performed under load control conditions and the fatigue load was applied in a sinusoidal form. The fatigue tests were loaded with maximum stress equal to 80% of the maximum strength, stress ratio ($\kappa = \sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max}$) equal to 0.1, and frequency between 1 to 10 Hz. The final failure mode for out-plane shear fatigue tests was nearly the same as the final failure mode of static experiments. An edge view picture of the specimens, failed under out-of-plane shear static and fatigue loading, is shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Edge view of out-of-plane shear specimens, failed under (a) static and (b) fatigue loading

The fatigue life of the material was measured for different samples by applying the maximum interlaminar shear stress (σ_{yz}) equal to a percentage of the maximum interlaminar shear strength and stress ratio equal to 0.1. Tests were continued till catastrophic failure was achieved. The results of fatigue life tests are summarized in Table 2.

Specimen Code	Percent of Max. Strength	Frequency (Hz)	Number of Cycles to failure
F-1	80.	2.	3068
F-2	80	2.	3528
F-3	70.	2.	8991
F-4	70.	2.	10789
F-5	60.	1-10.	1245373
F-6	60.	1-10.	1469540

Table 2. Results of fatigue life tests

It is clear that to characterize the interlaminar shear properties of the material (fatigue life and residual strength) more tests must be performed. Although a limited number of fatigue tests are shown, a reasonable scatter was achieved which shows the reliability of the test method.

CONCLUSIONS

The double notched specimen test method is verified as a simple and reliable test method to measure the interlaminar shear properties of composite materials. No complicated fixture is required for this method which is beneficial in fatigue testing of the materials. Out-of-plane buckling, due to antisymmetric geometry of the specimen, can be eliminated by using a simple clamp. The results of stress analysis, using a finite element technique, of the double notched specimen show that by selecting the proper geometry, a suitable and uniform state of interlaminar shear stress (σ_{yz}) can be achieved on the gage area. Also results show the magnitudes of the other stresses in the gage length region (σ_{yy} , and σ_{zz}) are not as critical compared to interlaminar shear stress (σ_{yz}). The failed specimens under static and fatigue loading conditions show nearly the same final failure mode in the gage area. The results of the experimental studies for static and fatigue cases show a reasonable scatter for the magnitude of static strength and fatigue life of the material, which confirm the reliability of the test method.

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